

TRENDS IN CARTOGRAPHY OF CHILD DEVELOPMENT AND VIRTUAL REALITY: A BIBLIOMETRIC ANALYSIS

CRISTINA PÁEZ-QUINDE

Carrera De Desarrollo De Aplicaciones Web – Instituto Tecnológico Superior Universitario España. Ambato – Ecuador. Email: maria.paez@iste.edu.ec

IBETH MOLINA-ARCOS

Carrera De Marketing – Instituto Tecnológico Superior Universitario España. Ambato – Ecuador. Email: lbeth.molina@iste.edu.ec

JORGE CÁRDENAS-MEDINA

Coordinador De La Salud – Instituto Tecnológico Superior Universitario España. Ambato – Ecuador. Email: Jorge.cardenas@iste.edu.ec

DONALD REYES-BEDOYA

Carrera De Desarrollo De Aplicaciones Web – Instituto Tecnológico Superior Universitario España. Ambato – Ecuador. Email: donald.reyes@iste.edu.ec

Abstract

In this scientific article, a bibliometric analysis was conducted to examine the cartographic trends related to child development and virtual reality. The study was based on the compilation and analysis of data from relevant scientific articles in academic databases with impact factor, aiming to identify the main thematic areas and their relationships. The results revealed a growing interest in the topic of child development and virtual reality, as well as related fields such as gamification, virtual environments, video games, serious games, reflected in the increased scientific production in recent years. Four main categories were identified: cognitive development, socioemotional development, technology-mediated learning, and physical and linguistic development, representing different aspects of comprehensive child development and how virtual reality can influence them. The analysis also showed that these thematic areas are interconnected, emphasizing the importance of addressing child development comprehensively and considering multiple dimensions simultaneously. It was found that virtual reality has been used to enhance cognitive, socioemotional, physical, and linguistic skills by creating interactive virtual environments. This bibliometric study provides insight into current trends in the field of child development and virtual reality. It highlights the importance of considering child development comprehensively and the interconnectedness among different thematic areas. These findings offer a solid foundation for future research and applications in this field.

Keywords: Bibliometric Analysis, Virtual Environments, Child Development, Cognitive Development, Interactive Virtual Environments.

INTRODUCTION

Bibliometric analysis is a valuable tool for the development of research lines in various fields of knowledge. This methodology is based on the quantitative analysis of scientific production and allows identifying trends, emerging topics, collaborations among researchers, and the evolution of research in a specific area.

This analysis is carried out through the collection and analysis of bibliographic data, such as scientific articles, citations, specialized journals, and other academic documents. The data is processed using statistical techniques and visualization tools, which facilitates the identification of patterns and trends in scientific literature (Ahuja & Polascik, The digital

metaverse: Applications in artificial intelligence, medical education, and integrative health, 2023).

One of the main applications of bibliometric analysis is the identification of promising research areas. By analyzing scientific production and citations in a specific field, emerging topics and areas with higher research activity can be detected (Ahuja y otros, 2023). Additionally, it allows identifying key researchers and collaboration networks in a particular area. Analyzing co-authorships and citations among researchers can establish connections between experts and promote scientific collaboration. This collaboration can strengthen existing research lines and open up new opportunities for interdisciplinary research (Bloom y otros, 2023).

Another important application of bibliometric analysis is tracking and evaluating scientific production. By analyzing bibliometric indicators, such as journal impact factor, the number of citations received by an article, or an investigator's h-index, the quality and impact of research can be assessed. This provides relevant information for decision-making in research project planning and resource allocation (Ching-Leng & Chiu-Lin, 2023).

For this research, the field of comprehensive child development is combined, considering trends in new learning processes mediated by technologies, preferably those that are part of the teaching-learning process in the context of technical and technological education (Deng & Romainoor, 2022).

Comprehensive Child Development

Comprehensive child development encompasses different aspects of children's growth, such as their cognitive, socioemotional, physical, and linguistic development. During the early years of life, children experience rapid development and acquisition of fundamental skills (Diogo y otros, 2023).

Comprehensive child development is characterized as a multidimensional, continuous, and individual process in which children acquire skills and competencies in different areas. Each child experiences a unique and progressive development, influenced by their environment and social interactions. Through interaction with their surroundings, children actively learn by exploring and participating in experiences that allow them to acquire knowledge and skills (Diwani & Mohammed, 2023).

Table 1: Comprehensive Child Development by Stages

	0 to 12 months	1 to 2 years	2 to 4 years	4 to 8 years
Motor development	Capable of grasping small objects with the hand. Can already hold up the head before reaching the first year.	Takes their first steps with assistance. Gradually starts walking on their own. By the end of this stage, they can run, jump,	Can throw a ball high and even jump on one foot. Established hand preference.	Displays perfect movements and acquires new motor skills.

		and go up and down stairs.		
Cognitive	Reacts to pleasant stimuli. Displays emotions such as anger, irritation, happiness, and joy.	Can relate the story they hear with the illustrations in children's tales	Capable of understanding more complex concepts. Memory becomes more consolidated.	Their ideas are grounded in reality and no longer confused with fantasies.
Language - communication	Crying is their main means of communication. "Social smile" emerges.	Has a vocabulary of about 50 words. Can respond with a "yes" or a "no."	Has a vocabulary of around 1000 words. Constructs sentences. Improved communication.	Clearly expresses what they want and what they think. Constructs sentences grammatically perfectly.
Social - emotional	Actively interacts with those around them.	Expresses more complex feelings such as embarrassment, pride, and jealousy.	Becomes more independent and enjoys autonomy. Does not have full control over emotions but communicates better.	Their feelings are more enduring. Is aware of their emotions and capable of expressing or concealing them. Empathy emerges.

Additionally, child development is also influenced by biological and genetic factors, and the plasticity of the infant brain is highlighted, allowing experiences and the environment to shape their development. In summary, understanding the characteristics of comprehensive child development is essential to provide a supportive environment and appropriate learning opportunities for each child (*Hernon y otros, 2023*).

Sustainable Development Goals and Early Childhood

The sustainable development agenda was adopted in 2015 by approximately 193 countries, where 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) were established for the international community, aiming to achieve a more equitable and sustainable life for all individuals, regardless of age, gender, or ethnicity (*Hung-Ming y otros, 2023*).

The SDGs promote children's rights and offer the opportunity to protect all boys and girls with the commitment of leaving no one behind. Therefore, the SDGs also present an opportunity for Ecuador (*Jean-Baptiste, 2023*).

The Agenda 2030 requires ensuring the well-being of children. To enforce these objectives, a political and social approach is needed that considers the needs of children, especially those in vulnerable situations.

Table 2: SDGs Linked to the Research

SDG	Description
	<p>In Ecuador, over 28% of girls and boys as adolescents live in poverty, and 10% in extreme poverty.</p>
	<p>37% of girls and boys as adolescents between the ages of 8 to 16 in Ecuador are overweight or obese.</p>
	<p>In Ecuador, it is estimated that 45% of girls and boys from rural areas drop out of school early.</p>

Virtual Reality

In this context, virtual reality (VR) has become a promising tool to stimulate and foster comprehensive child development. VR provides immersive and interactive experiences that can facilitate learning and exploration in multiple dimensions (Kamm y otros, 2023).

In the cognitive domain, VR can offer virtual educational environments that challenge creativity, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills in children. Through interactive activities, children can enhance their spatial, memory, and attention skills. Regarding socioemotional development, VR can create safe and controlled environments where children can explore different social situations and practice social skills (Khalid y otros, 2023). By interacting with virtual avatars, children can develop empathy, emotional recognition, and interpersonal communication skills. In the physical aspect, VR can promote motor development and coordination through virtual games and physical activities. By performing movements and actions in virtual environments, children can improve their balance, hand-eye coordination, and fine motor skills (Maketo y otros, 2023).

Figure 1. Characteristics of Virtual Reality

In addition, VR can stimulate linguistic development by providing immersive environments where children can interact with virtual characters and engage in storytelling activities. This can enrich their vocabulary, oral comprehension, and verbal expression. It is important to exercise caution and supervise the use of VR in children, setting time limits, and ensuring their physical and emotional safety during virtual experiences (Maravilla y otros, 2023).

Virtual reality offers exciting opportunities to promote comprehensive child development. Through interactive virtual environments, children can enhance their cognitive, socioemotional, physical, and linguistic skills. However, responsible, and appropriate implementation must be considered to ensure that VR benefits and safeguards children's development (Meng-Chun y otros, 2023).

The benefits of including augmented reality activities in preschool learning are as follows:

1. Stimulate interest in learning: linking visual and auditory information to real contexts can encourage meaningful learning and curiosity in children.
2. Develop attention, memory, concentration, reasoning, and conflict resolution, among other important developmental skills.
3. Conceptualize a specific topic.
4. Enhance the learning experience allows for a better understanding of complex issues that may be challenging to comprehend on paper but become easier to understand through sensorimotor experiences that clearly exemplify what is being taught.

5. Helps children with social skill issues connect virtual elements with emotions, enhancing their development.
6. Includes a variety of learning levels allows children to overcome different levels of difficulty, enabling them to strengthen and acquire new knowledge.

Gamification

Gamification, which involves incorporating game elements and techniques into non-playful contexts, is receiving increasing attention in the field of comprehensive child development (Talbi & Boudemagh-Souad, 2022). The combination of play and learning has proven to be an effective strategy to promote cognitive, socioemotional, physical, and linguistic development in children. It is equally important to consider the proper process of gamification in the classroom (Pözl-Stefanec & Geißler, 2022):

Figura 1: Círculo de Deming de la Gamificación

In cognitive terms, gamification offers opportunities to improve skills such as problem-solving, critical thinking, and creativity. Games designed specifically to stimulate cognitive development present progressive challenges that promote logical and strategic reasoning in children.

In the socioemotional domain, gamification can help children develop important social and emotional skills. Collaborative games foster cooperation, communication, and teamwork, while virtual role-playing games allow them to practice social skills in a safe environment (Ullah y otros, 2022).

Regarding physical development, gamification can promote physical activity and motor development through interactive games that require bodily movements. These games can improve children's motor coordination, balance, and physical strength, encouraging a healthy and active lifestyle.

In the linguistic aspect, gamification offers opportunities to enrich language development. Word games, puzzles, and interactive reading and writing activities can enhance

children's vocabulary, oral comprehension, and verbal expression, strengthening their language skills (Yang, C.; Huang, C.; Su, J., 2020).

It is important to consider that gamification should be implemented in a balanced and appropriate manner. Games should be adapted to each child's developmental level and individual needs, ensuring they are challenging yet achievable. Additionally, time limits should be set, and the content of the games should be supervised to ensure a safe and beneficial experience (Zhai & Jackson, 2023).

METHODOLOGY

In this bibliometric study, it was necessary to mention that there are different types of research, such as exploratory, descriptive, correlational, and explanatory. Furthermore, the strategies used during the research should be explained. In the case of this bibliometric study, a retrospective-descriptive approach was employed. Retrospective studies use historical information to examine events that have occurred in the past. The temporal period covered by this study can be extensive, and an advantage of retrospective studies is that they require little time to complete, as they only involve recording and analyzing data.

Based on the above, the research was carried out retrospectively on recognized databases such as Scielo, PubMed, Web of Science, and Elsevier. A search for scientific articles was conducted over a 10-year period addressing research on child development and virtual reality. Additionally, this research project aims to describe the current state and trends in research on these topics from a lifecycle perspective in the last ten years.

Hernández, Collado, and Lucio (2010) define the descriptive scope as the identification of important characteristics and features of any analyzed phenomenon, as well as the description of trends in a group, communities, processes, objects, or any other phenomenon subject to analysis (Bloom y otros, 2023).

RESULTS

For this bibliometric study, 197 scientific productions were found in different high-impact databases. It is also evident that there are 10 works with patents focused on child development, with around 155 citations; finally, 6,862 co-cited documents were identified.

Figure 3: General Search Information

The information generated in Figure 3 serves as the starting point for the results presented below, based on the search trends for child development and virtual reality.

Figure 4: Child Development Publication Timeline

For Figure 4, the timeline is visualized where research focused on child development and virtual reality began in 1991 with scientific production centered on child development. From the years 1995 to 1999, 10 journal articles were published on topics such as "The virtues of virtual: A review of Tiffin and Rajasingham's In Search of the Virtual Class and Hiltz's The Virtual Classroom," and "Biodesensitization: Biofeedback-controlled systematic desensitization of the stress response to infant crying."

From the year 2000 to 2010, there was an increased trend in publication in the field of child development with a total of 51 journal articles and a conference proceedings book. The published topics were focused on "An autonomous educational mobile robot mediator," "Respiratory, postural and spatio-kinetic motor stabilization, internal models, top-down timed motor coordination and expanded cerebello-cerebral circuitry: a review," and "Action and the representation of distance in cognitive maps acquired through imagined traversal: the development of a new methodology."

From the year 2011 to 2020, there were a total of 84 journal articles, one book, one book chapter, two patents, and a conference proceedings article. This time range represents a deeper exploration of these two fields of study. The documents that executed patents were "Interventions to improve gross motor performance in children with neurodevelopmental disorders: a meta-analysis," "Enrobotment or toy robots in the developing brain," "Using a virtual reality game to assess goal-directed hand movements in children: A pilot feasibility study," "Route-learning strategies in typical and atypical development; eye tracking reveals atypical landmark selection in Williams syndrome."

From the year 2021 to the present, there are 36 scientific productions, mostly journal articles, with the year 2022 having the highest number of productions focusing on "Interactive Virtual Reality versus Vignette-Based Assessment of Children's Aggressive Social Information Processing," "Could virtual reality applications pose real risks to children and adolescents? A systematic review of ethical issues and concerns," "The Foundations and Frontiers of Research on the Effect of Video Games on Child Development," "Using virtual reality to treat aggressive behavior problems in children: A feasibility study," and "The Role of Perspective Taking and Self-Control in a Preventive Intervention Targeting Childhood Disruptive Behavior."

Figure 5: Co-cited Fields of Study

Figure 5 displays the number of co-cited keywords according to the field of study, as visualized in Psychology (121); Medicine (58); Computer Science (46); Virtual Reality (42); Developmental psychology (38); Cognition (36); Psychiatry (28); Cognitive Psychology (25); Autism (25); Artificial intelligence (21); Multimedia (21); and Intervention (20). These are the areas where child development and virtual reality have the most significant trends.

Table 3: Author Coreferences

Authors	Coreferences
Baron-Cohen, S.	926
Hegarty, M.	924
Montello D.R.	912
Burgess, N.	720
Slater, M.	693
Loomis, J.M.	660
Golledge, R.G.	635
Newcombe, N.S.	632
Maguire, E.A.	534

Table 3 displays the co-references of the top authors within the established research fields for this study, from which the following information can be derived:

Baron-Cohen, S. has a total of 926 co-references and a reference strength per 10 articles of 51,373. Similarly, Hegarty, M. (924) with a reference strength of 58,506; Montello D.R. with (912) and 72,699 references per scientific production; Burgess, N. (720) with a reference strength of 76,081 in scientific productions; Slater, M. has a total of 693 citations

and a reference strength of 76,081 in terms of co-reference. From this resulting information, it can be concluded that most authors have a strong level of co-references per article, as is the case with Burgess, N., Professor of Cognitive Neuroscience at University College London, who has an H-index of 99 and an H-index 10 of 194. The article with the highest number of citations is "The human hippocampus and spatial and episodic memory" with a total of 2,844 citations.

Figure 2: Clusters de autores

Figure 6 shows author networks defined by the co-citation strength in scientific productions. Eight clusters can be identified, each composed of a specific number of authors:

- Cluster 1: A total of 263 authors, including the most cited ones, with co-citation strength greater than 76,081 in scientific productions.
- Cluster 2: Comprising 225 authors, notable figures include Slater, M.; Cohen, J.; Piaget, J.; Frith, C.D.; Decety, J.; Rizzolatti, G.
- Cluster 3: Consisting of 17 authors, with co-citation strength among Thomson, J.A.; Lee, D.D.; Barton, B.K., and Schwebel, DC. Another subnetwork includes Plumert, J.M.; Morrongiello, B.A., with Adolph, K.E. from Cluster 2.
- Cluster 4: This cluster contains 27 authors such as Anderson, V.; Catroppa, C.; Taylor, H.G.; Yeates, K.O., and Stancin, T., with a co-citation strength of 123 co-citations in scientific productions with the author Chapman, S. from Cluster 6.
- Cluster 5: With 188 authors, establishing three consolidated subnetworks between this cluster and Clusters 6, 4, and 7. Authors with higher co-citation include Ekman, P.; Eisenberg, N.; Dodge, K.A.; Gross, J.; Rothbaum, B.O.

- Cluster 6: This cluster comprises 104 authors generating a subnetwork within the same cluster of 50 authors. Pioneering co-citations include Baron-Cohen, S.; Frith, U.; Person, S.; Charman, T.; Mitchell, P.; Rutter, M.; Happe, F.; Robins, B., and Dautenhahn, K., forming a network with Breazeal, C. from Cluster 8.
- Cluster 7: Composed of 7 authors like Carotenuto, M.; Cipolotti, L.; Maltese, A.; Parisi, L.; Rocella, M., who create an internal network with a co-citation strength of 1324 references in scientific productions.
- Cluster 8: This cluster has 169 authors, including Bandura, A.; Anderson, C.A., who form a subnetwork with Cluster 5 with Barlow, D.H. and Beck, A.T.; Ryan, R.M.; and Deci, E.L., and finally with Mayer, R.E.; and Bavelier, D.; who generate a subnetwork with Cluster 1 with Hegarty, M.

Figure 7: Formation of Subnetworks

In Figure 7, the subnetworks formed within some of the clusters generated by VoS Viewer are evident. For example, in Cluster A, Cluster 1 exhibits co-reference strength with Cluster 2, meaning that Frith, C.D. is related to a group of authors such as Maguire, E.A.; Hegarty, M.; Golledge, R.G.

In Figure 7B, multiple subnetworks are observed between Clusters 4, 8, 6, 5, and 2. Anderson, V; has a direct co-citation with Baron-Cohen, S., Achenbach, T.M., Li, X., and Bater, E. This generates channels of scientific production and enables the creation of new lines of research related to child development and virtual reality.

In Figure 7C, subnetworks of research and scientific production are similarly generated between Freeman, D. (5), Frith, C.D. (2), and Burgess, N. (1). On the other hand, Baron-Cohen, S. (6) is related to Dolan, R.J. (2), Frith, C.D. (2), and Berthoz, A. (1)..

Figure 8: Citation by Cities per Year

For this analysis, the maximum number of countries per document is taken into account, which in this case is 25 out of a total of 140 countries. A scientific mapping of 58 country citations is generated. The United States has 559 high-impact indexed productions in Scopus; Canada has 360 documents with a citation strength of 13,355 references in scientific productions. Germany has 329 articles with impact factor and a country citation of 10,801 references. China has 318 articles with a citation strength of 3,441 references. Australia has 300 scientific productions with a country citation strength of 10,852. Brazil has 58 impact factor productions in Scopus with a reference of 352 citations. Argentina has 9 documents with a citation of 57 references per document. Regarding Ecuador, it has 7 scientific productions with a citation strength of 15 references.

Figure 9: Co-occurrence of Keywords

CONCLUSIONS

Virtual reality has the potential to be a beneficial tool for comprehensive child development in various areas. It offers immersive and interactive experiences that can enrich children's learning and exploration of the world around them (Meng-Chun y otros, 2023). However, it is crucial to consider responsible and appropriate implementation of virtual reality in child development. Time limits for usage should be established, and the physical and emotional safety of children during virtual experiences must be ensured.

Moreover, this field should not replace real-world interactions and experiences but rather complement them. It is essential for children to also engage in physical, social, and linguistic activities outside the virtual environment for a balanced comprehensive development. Similarly, it can be a powerful tool to stimulate comprehensive child development, improving cognitive, socioemotional, physical, and linguistic skills. However, its implementation should be careful and balanced to ensure optimal benefits and protect the well-being of children during its use.

Research Directions:

- Attention and protection of children's rights based on m-learning.
- Gamification in contributing to the comprehensive development of children aged 0 to 5 in different contexts.
- Pedagogical and intercultural iconographic virtual environments in attention and protection of children's rights.
- Design, execution, and evaluation of processes related to early childhood care and education based on neurotechnology.
- Mobile health in comprehensive child development in various contexts.
- Quality in early childhood education and care based on neuroeducation.
- Development of early stimulation through TAC for quality education.
- Cultural education and protection of early childhood.

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